

CURE PROCESS DESIGN TO MANUFACTURE COMPOSITE COMPONENTS WITH VARIABLE THICKNESS BY A CLOSED DIE TECHNOLOGY.

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SUMMARY

Composite components with variable thickness are particularly sensitive to the cure cycle imposed that for such components can cause a no constant temperature field and a cure degree field. The heat generated by the cure process can cause a premature polymerization in the parts with small thickness or an excessive temperature in the innermost part with high thickness. In this paper a preliminary design methodology of the cure cycle is defined.

Keywords: closed die technology, variable thickness components, cure degree, cure cycle.

INTRODUCTION

In the manufacture of polymer-matrix composite components by closed die technology structural and geometrical/dimensional unconformities can be found such as to determine damages and the rejection of end-items. In most cases, these problems are caused by a wrong design of cure process in terms of thermal cycle and tooling. The geometrical and dimensional unconformities, that can compromise part assembling, show themselves in variation between real and nominal conditions, and are caused by phenomena that happen during mould heating/cooling. Structural defects, such as resin degradation and component failure, are caused by phenomena that happen during both heating and maintenance at high temperature phase and cooling phase. During heating phase there can be resin degradation: polymerization is an exothermic reaction, and the resin's low thermal conductivity gets heat developed in the component to not be drained outside in times consistent with those of reaction, therefore heat piles up and raises temperature, sometimes over that expected in the thermal cycle, so matrix degradation is reached. This problem is more important the more elevated component thickness is. High thickness laminates show other problems, related to the non uniform matrix polymerization. In fact, the low resin thermal conductivity does not let heat provided from outside to reach the inside in a very short time, so outer areas will polymerize before the inner ones. In order to resolve these problems it must be created a process model, able to describe the various phases happening during polymerization in order to design a local thermal cycle, or variable depending on component shape/thickness.

Development of adequate tools for the prediction of shape distortions is considered as an important step towards a more cost efficient development, improved performance and optimised manufacturing of composites [1, 2]. In the literature is possible to find out some example related to simulation of polymerization cycle of composites, but these cases regard geometries with constant thickness [3-12]. The aim is to fix an integrated design methodology for cure cycle and forming tools, in order to obtain a component consistent with required specifications [13, 16]. The present work, that is a first step toward the definition of an aforesaid methodology, has this target: to carry out FEM analysis and preliminary optimization of cure cycle of a variable thickness component, putting particular attention to the thermochemical effect of the cycle.

FEA SOFTWARE VERIFY FOR THE SIMULATION OF THE POLYMERIZATION CYCLE.

The software used to design the thermal cycle for variable thickness components is Comsol Multiphysics. To verify the software reliability it is necessary to test it by similar known results or by experimental tests. As there are no experimental data, thermochemical models already existing in literature are implemented on utilized software, even if they concern simple geometries. It is carried out the simulation of data obtained by Olofsson [5], that regard constant thickness composite pipe manufactured by filament winding technology. In this model there are no convective heat exchange, so energy equation is in the form as equation:

$$\rho_c \cdot c_{p,c} \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = \nabla(k_c \nabla T) + \rho_r V_r H_r \frac{d\alpha}{dt} \quad (1)$$

where V_r is the resin volume fraction, moreover physical properties of the material are not considered constant and they are fixed by relations:

$$c_{p,c} = (V_r \rho_r c_{p,r} + V_f \rho_f c_{p,f}) / \rho_c, \quad c_{p,r} = D_1 + (D_2 + D_3 \alpha)T + D_4 \alpha \quad (2)$$

$$k_r = D_5 + (D_6 T + D_7) \alpha, \quad \rho_c = \rho_r V_r + \rho_f V_f \quad (3)$$

in which subscript r refer to resin, f to fibres and c to composite, V_i is the mass fraction ($V_f = 0.64$, $V_r = 1 - V_f$), and D_i coefficients are some constants calculated with experimental curve fitting. The transversal thermal conductivity is obtainable by Nielsen equations [5]:

$$\frac{k_c}{k_r} = \frac{1 + ABV_f}{1 - B\psi V_f}, \quad A = k_E - 1, \quad B = \frac{(k_f/k_r) - 1}{(k_f/k_r) + A}, \quad \psi = 1 + \left(\frac{1 - V_{f,max}}{V_{f,max}^2} \right) V_f \quad (4)$$

Where k_E is the generalised Einstein coefficient (1.84), $V_{f,max}$ is the maximum fiber volume fraction with recommended value 0.82 [5]. Polymerization reaction follows the autocatalytic model:

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = (k_1 + k_2 \alpha^m)(\alpha_{max} - \alpha)^n \quad (5)$$

in which the factor k_1 , the factor k_2 , the partial reaction order n, and the final degree of cure α_{max} are fixed as a function of temperature as in equations as:

$$k_1 = 0, \quad k_2 = A_{c,2} \exp\left(-\frac{E_2}{RT}\right); \quad n = a + bT; \quad m = 0.3; \quad \alpha_{max} = pT + q \quad (6)$$

(k_2 is Arrhenius relation) in which E_2 is activation energy, R is the universal gas constant and $A_{c,2}$ is frequency factor. The value of coefficients are in Table 1 [5].

As boundary condition, convective heat flow is imposed on material and thermal insulation on die, since the die is closed ends and the heat capacity of air is very small. The parameters used in this simulation are obtained from literature. Oven temperature follows a thermal cycle as that in Figure 1-a, that is marked out by two temperature steps: the former is at 80°C and the latter at 140°C. In Figure 1-a the temperature versus time in a point in the centre of pipe wall is showed. In this Figure there is a light peak due to the heat of reaction, but only in step at 80°C, while it disappears in step at 140°C, because most of reaction occurs in the first temperature step. In the Figures 1-a,b there are literature data obtained by experimental and simulation activity [5]. In particular in Figure 1-b is showed the cure degree trend in the centre of material. At the end of the first temperature step at 80°C there is no a complete polymerization of material, in fact the degree of cure is about 0.7, but the full polymerization can be obtained raising temperature to second step. The results obtained by software Comsol show a light difference with the literature data.

Figure 1. a) Temperature trend in pipe wall; b) Cure degree trend in pipe wall

Simulation of polymerization cycle of a variable thickness component

In this work it is paid attention to the design of thermal cycle for variable thickness components that present a non uniform behaviour during polymerization. A very critical combination of geometry and material characteristics is chosen. The material is a prepreg of unidirectional glass fibres and epoxy resin, whose data, extracted from literature [5], are in Table 1. The chosen benchmark shows the same critical states, in terms of thickness variable, of a rotorcraft structural component. This component presents a variable thickness geometry, in fact the widest section, in root zone, is about 50 mm thick, while the smallest, in the vertex, only 5 mm; the overall length is about 1400 mm. The mould consists of two parts: once they are assembled, an internal cavity is created, that presents a variable section along mould axis. This is represented in Figure 2. Tools and press surfaces are made with steel S355JR (Fe510b), while the component is constituted by prepreg of unidirectional glass fibres and epoxy resin. Abovementioned material presents a cure temperature between 105-135°C and starts to degrade at 140°C. Strips of prepreg are appropriately disposed in the cavity of a half mould, respecting the correct fibres direction in the real component. At the end of stratification, the mould is closed and sent to press, that has two surfaces parallel to the ground between which the mould is positioned. In the press planes there are some ducts through which oil passes. The oil is heated by an external boiler, and it provides or removes heat from the system, so the temperature that is controlled is oil one. The compacting pressure is furnished by hydraulic jack, that are set out along press contour.

The problems considered happen during heating and curing at high temperature, so in this work only these two phases are considered, omitting cooling. At process beginning, the heat makes resin viscosity rapidly decrease and it begins to flow because of pressure gradient between material and environment. Most flow takes place when viscosity is at lower value. Providing more heat cross-linking begins, so viscosity raises till flow stops. During cure process permanence at intermediate temperature (dwell) is expected: it allows the viscosity to remain at lower value for a long period, assuring a greater resin flow and a more uniform compacting than the case without dwell [3].

Figure 2. Benchmark: 1,3: male and female moulds; 2: variable thickness component

Table 1. Parameters of analysed composite (glass fibres and epoxy resin)

Physical Property	Value	Physical Property	Value	Physical Property	Value
c_{pr} [J/(kgK)]	840	k_f [W/(mK)]	0.93	H_r [J/g]	368
$A_{c,2}$ [1/s]	$1.24 \cdot 10^7$	E_2 [kJ/mol]	74.68	p	-1.1172
q	0.0051484	a	-4.2589	b	0.013457
D_1 [J/(kg°C)]	1694.1	D_2 [J/(kg°C ²)]	2.907	D_3 [J/(kg°C ²)]	0.502
D_4 [J/(kg°C)]	-668.1	D_5 [W/(m°C)]	0.14	D_6 [W/(m°C ²)]	0.00065
D_7 [W/(m°C)]	0.035	ρ_r [kg/m ³]	1175	ρ_f [kg/m ³]	2540

The common problem in the cure cycle design of a composite material manufacturing is how to set-up the time–temperature profile in such a way that certain criteria are fulfilled and the result is optimal. As the simulation tool allows for the tracking of all the features of the curing process at each time-step and thickness, several optimality criteria can be introduced in order to attain the optimal results with respect to the overall process performance [13]. Once features and process parameters are identified, process can be implemented in FEM software. Regarding the examined component, process modelling and analysis are very heavy from a computational point of view, so the three-dimensional model is replaced by a two-dimensional one. In this model four characteristic sections are chosen: S1, S2, S3 and SL. The former three are cross section while the latter is the component symmetry plane. Section disposition is reported in Figure 3. Component thickness is variable, and each section plane is marked out by different thicknesses, that rise from S3 to S1.

Figure 3. Sections on benchmark

As aforesaid, heat is provided to press by means of oil that is heated outside and then passes through apposite pipes in the press planes, so the complete 2D model must represent the mould with the prepreg inside and press planes with oil channels, but there will be an increase of model complexity, that implies more time and computer memory. So press planes are removed from model, moreover on mould contour that was in contact with them it was applied thermal cycle that planes formerly provided and oil cycle is not considered. Practically thermal interaction between oil, plane and mould are bypassed, with related problems of conduction and heat inertia, applying thermal cycle of HS surface in Figure 4. Once fixed the cycle it will be necessary to calculate that one of oil, through computer simulation.

Simulation of cure cycle on middle section

For a preliminary analysis of thermal cycle effects on the component section S2 is considered, because here laminate thickness has a middle value. The section of the component in the mould is shown in Figure 4.a, where the geometry and thermal boundary condition of the FEA model are shown. Heat is provided on lower and upper surfaces, marked as HS (Heat Source), while thermal insulation is considered on side ones (TI, Thermal Insulation), because thermal flux on these faces is negligible. In order to monitor cure phenomenon, four points were considered: A, B, C and D. In Figure 4-b, A, B, and D are on a horizontal segment in the centre of the laminate, while C is on its upper vertex; both C and D are on the interface between component and mould.

At this point FEA model can be implemented. Conduction heat exchange only are considered in energy equation, because the convection ones are very little, so the relation used is (1) where cure rate is calculated by means of an autocatalytic model (5) and (6). Physical characteristic of this composite material, such as thermal conductivity, density and specific heat, are calculated from the ones of fibres and matrix by relations (2 - 4). Two hypothesis are considered for the thermal cycle defined: i) two temperature dwells; ii) evaluation of thermo-chemical phenomena only. Referring to company experience a waiting time $D2 = 60$ min is imposed in the first dwell (first dwell condition), whereas for heating rate is imposed an utmost rate of $2.4^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$. Regarding expected output the following conditions are considered: i) higher temperature must not exceed the critical one, equal to 140°C , for avoiding resin degradation; ii) final degree of cure must be 0.95; iii) dwell temperature is 77°C . From condition ii, by equation (6), the utmost cycle temperature is about 128°C . For first attempt, a thermal cycle with two temperature dwell (I-TC) is imposed in HS. Heating rate for both dwell is $2.4^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$. Imposed thermal cycle is in Figure 5-a, while the measured one and the degree of cure in points of interest are in Figure 5-b, 5-c and 6-a. From these Figure it can be seen that thermal profile of points C and D is very similar to that one imposed in HS, so the

conditions on maximum temperature and on final degree of cure are respected. On the contrary, thermal profile in points A and B is more different from that imposed, in fact in the first dwell the condition $D2=60$ min is not respected because T_{dwell} temperature is maintained only for $t=52$ min (see * in Figure 5-b), moreover straight after first temperature increase the temperature exceed both imposed and maximum one (see ** in Figure 5-b). The above exothermic peak is due to the fact that at the end of the first dwell a lot of resin is not cured yet and polymerizes at higher temperature, so the reaction is faster, according to the equations (5) and (6), and produced heat is not dissipated outside in time and it accumulates.

Figure 4. Section S2: a) thermal boundary condition with HS = Heat Source and TI = Thermal Insulation; b), critical points (A,B,C,D)

a)

b)

c)

Figure 5. a) Cure cycle defined on HS; b,c) Temperature in A, B, C e D points.

Basing on merely thermochemical considerations on output of I-TC a new thermal cycle with a wider dwell (1h 30') and a second temperature increase rate of $1.1^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$, marked as II-TC in Figure 5-a are defined. Simulation outputs of points A and B are in Figures 7-a,b, in which it can be seen that both conditions on permanence time on first dwell and on maximum temperature and degree of cure are respected. By means of this analysis on mean section the critical point among those chosen is identified, i.e. point A, in fact greater temperature gradient is between core and surface, as in Figure 8-a A similar approach is followed also for S1 and S3 sections, so other two critical points are identified in laminate core, therefore on section plane SL, as visible in Figure 8-b

Simulation of cure cycle on all component/tool

Generally this kind of component is polymerized applying a thermal cycle on the whole surface HS of the component/tools system. The choice of this cycle must obviously take into account the characteristics of each point in the laminate, so each zone with a different thickness has its own specifications, therefore basing on consideration on productive process the conditions in Table 2 are considered for the three different thicknesses. These conditions are on expected degree of cure, permanence time at first temperature dwell and critical temperature. In Figure 9-a and 9-b there are the outputs obtained applying the thermal cycle of S2 section (II-TC) to the whole component: in point E the constraints on dwell time and maximum temperature are not respected.

Table 2. Manufacturing conditions on the three sections S1, S2 and S3

	S1	S2	S3
Cure degree expected	0.95		
Time to first Dwell [min]	100 (= D1)	60 (= D2)	30 (= D3)
Critical Temperature [°C]	140		

Figure 9. Temperature and cure degree in points E, A and F (II-TC).

Afterwards a thermal cycle optimized for section S1 (III-TC, see also in Figure 5-a) is imposed. This cycle satisfies all conditions as reported in Figures 10-a,b: i) all dwells are respected; ii) there is a light exothermic peak that is negligible for the matrix; iii) the cure degree reaches the expected value of 0.95 in E, A and F points.

Figure 10. Temperature and cure degree in points E, A and F (III-TC).

PRELIMINARY OPTIMIZATION OF CURE CYCLE

Therefore the thermal cycle optimized for thicker section is the optimal also for the other two, but the thermal energy provided is not optimized: the thinner section remains at first dwell temperature for 2h 40', i.e. 2h 10' more respect to requested time, and the mean section remains at high temperature 1h 20'. In other words the system must keep a constant temperature (77°C) for 2h 40' also for sections that request less time. This does not advantage cure process in these sections, but provokes a considerable thermal loss towards environment, so the cycle for the thicker section does not optimize the process from an energetic point of view, even if it respects the imposed conditions.

Therefore the thermal profile can be optimized considering a differentiated cycle, i.e. considering an appropriate cycle for each thickness. This can be obtained adopting a differentiate heat source: as visible in Figures 11-a,b, the HS surfaces are subdivided into three parts (HS1, HS2 and HS3), and an appropriate thermal cycle is applied to each one. The cycle must be suitably defined, for example making use of the following constraint: in each critical point the same maximum degree of cure must be reached simultaneously. In Figure 11-b there is an early temperature profile combination and in Figure 12-a,b there is its output in terms of temperature and degree of cure. In Figure 13 there is the temperature field at different time on longitudinal section.

Figure 11. Differentiate thermal cycle

Figure 12. Results with differentiate thermal cycle: a) temperature; b) cure degree

Figure 13. Temperature distribution results vs. time simulation

CONCLUSIONS

In this work it is paid attention to the design of thermal cycle for variable thickness components that present a non uniform behaviour during polymerization. In order to resolve this question, the first step is analysing cure models in literature, usable for mathematical modelling and so for simulation of polymerization thermochemical phenomena. Then a software fit for simulation and management of complex operation is chosen. From a thermochemical point of view, the main problems discovered during composite component production are exothermic peak and the correct permanence at low viscosity, that influences compacting, excess resin ejection and void reduction. The aim is to optimize thermal profile through considerations on thermochemical behaviour of produced component. So a component and a composite material, retained critical for abovementioned questions, are chosen, then thermochemical phenomena of polymerization process are simulated. This research points out some aspects for variable thickness laminate not much analysed yet, for which a particular attention must be paid for the definition of the thermal cycle. The more critical sections are those thicker, and the thermal cycle of the whole component is referred to them. Obviously, thinner sections are less critical and almost always respect imposed conditions, even if the thermal profile chosen is highly oversized. In fact, a consequence is a too much long waiting at the dwell, that does not improve component quality (on the contrary it can deteriorate it), but implies dissipation of thermal energy. The solution found in the present work is the application of a differentiate thermal cycle, i.e. depending on particular component thickness/geometry. For the studied component, it is designed a cycle in which the three sections present a temperature profile defined imposing the convergence of the degree of cure at imposed value (0.95). This work is a first step towards both optimization of variable thickness component polymerization process, in which problems inherent stresses will must be foreseen, and definition of advanced methodologies for the design of polymerization tools.

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